

Implementation of Fathul Muin's Teaching Material Books to Improve Santri Competence at Tanwirunnida' Mungkid Islamic Boarding School, Central Java

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ABSTRACT

Fathul Muin, book of fiqh by Sheikh Zakariya al-Ansari al-Maliki. Fiqh teaching material (Fathul Muin) consists of seven volumes, which have several components, including: First: discussing issues of chastity, prayer, fasting, zakat, pilgrimage and its laws. Second: Discussing the subject matter of buying and selling transactions and the law. Third: Marriage and its laws, and finally war and its laws. Types of R&D research and data collection techniques using observation, interviews, and documentation. The results of the research on educational material in the Book of Fathul Muin are very useful for students in understanding Ushul al-Fiqh and jurisprudence lessons, and the learning process becomes very interesting in addition to the fact that this educational material can be studied independently and equipped with communicative language.

INTRODUCTION

The teaching process is the delivery of knowledge to students using formal and informal channels, while the learning process requires several components including Ustadz, students, subjects being taught or knowledge (Rusman, 2018). *Fathul Muin* is a book by Sheikh Zakariya Al-Ansari Al-Maliki. This book is one of the most famous books of Maliki jurisprudence in the Islamic world. *Fathul Muin* is a major work that discusses various issues of Islamic law in the Maliki school of thought in simple, clear and easy-to-understand language.

This book consists of seven volumes covering different and important topics in Maliki fiqh, such as worship, transactions, marriage, inheritance, etc. Each chapter of this book has been systematically organized and fully explained, making it a useful guide for scholars, scholars and anyone who wants to study Maliki jurisprudence. *Fathul Muin* is also known for its comprehensive and complete contents of Islamic law. This book has been widely studied in various Islamic educational institutions as the main educational material in the study of Maliki jurisprudence. In addition, this book is often used as a reference in solving problems of Islamic law in everyday life.

One of *Fath Moin's* strengths is that the language used in this book is easily understood by the general public. The explanation given is not too technical so it makes it easier for the reader to understand the contents of the book. This book also contains a clear reference system, so that readers can explore the basics of Islamic law described in the book. In general, the *Book of Fathul Muin* is considered one of the most important and influential books of Maliki jurisprudence in the Islamic world. With easy-to-understand language and complete explanations, this book is a reference for many people in studying and understanding Islamic law.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

The curriculum occupies a central place in education because the curriculum can direct all activities to achieve educational goals (Chamisijatin & Permana, 2020; Hikmawati & Hosnan, 2022). *Azra's* approach occupies a major place in education because it is about determining the direction, content and process of education which ultimately determines the type and qualifications of graduates of an educational institution (Azra, 2018). In other languages, the curriculum is the main guideline for formal education, because the curriculum is an embodiment of the educational goals to be achieved (Arifin, 2020; Rusman, 2018).

Based on the reasons above, the researcher tried to develop the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School Mungkid in Central Java, Central Java by making educational materials by compiling theories or principles of fiqh (Kitab Fathul Muin) in a systematic, easy to understand and fun way, fiqh. The teaching material (Fath Al-Ma'in) has several components, including First: Discusses issues of chastity, prayer, fasting, zakat, pilgrimage and its laws. Second: Discussing the subject matter of buying and selling transactions and the law. Third: Marriage and its laws, and finally war and its laws. Al-Millibari (2018: 03).

A literature study on the Book of Fathul Muin, and it is possible to benefit from the following references: 1). Al-Baghdadi and Muhammad Al-Tanbih and the most respected of the nation's Islamic legislators. Beirut: Dar Al-Qalam, 1999. This book discusses the books of Islamic law and provides an explanation of Fathul Muin as one of the important books in the field of fiqh. 2). Salah al-Din and Hassan Fathul Muin in a short publication interpretation. Lebanon: Dar Al-Ilm for Millions, 2003. This book is a study of the book Fath Al-Maeen, focusing on aspects of interpretation and explanation of the arguments contained in the book. Shebib, TI (2022) 3). Al-Quraini, Fathul Muin and Al-Fakira with the characteristics of their teachings merge. Riyadh: Dar Al-Minhaj, 2010. This book describes the characteristics and legal principles of the Maliki school of thought contained in the book Fath Al-Mu'in. 4). Abushouq, A.I. 'Mahlan Gifted Libraries: Islamic Libraries of the Twentieth Century.' Journal of Islamic Studies, Vol. 21, no. 3, 2010, p. 339-356. This article discusses the collection of books at the Mahlan Library in Cairo, including Fath Moin's book. Rosedin, DN (2022). 5). Orihuela, J. 'Islamization of the Acehnese in the Seventeenth and Eighteenth Century: An Evaluation.' Islamic Studies, Vol. 23, no. 2, 2016, p. 215 - 256. This article comments on the influence of the book Fath Moin on the spread of the Maliki school of thought in Aceh, Indonesia. Azra, A.; (2016).

In conducting a literature review of the Book of Fathul Muin, it is important to find sources that provide in-depth and authoritative explanations about the book. In addition, it is also necessary to consider the author's point of view and approach in providing an analysis of the book. Studying the theory of essays in the Book of Fathul Muin, several theoretical approaches can be used as follows:

1). Historical Approach: By using this approach, the article can explain the origins of the Fathul Muin Book, its author, its historical context, its influence and its important role in the development of Islamic jurisprudence. That is, the article will discuss the history of the book and the importance of this work in

the world of Islamic scholars. 2). Literary Approach: This approach focuses on the analysis of the structure, writing style, and language used in the Fathul Muin Book. Essays can examine how the author uses certain language and writing styles to convey the fiqh concepts in the book. 3). Philosophical approach: This approach involves analyzing the fiqh concepts contained in the book Fath al-Mu'in. Articles can analyze the arguments and theoretical basis used in the book, as well as provide an understanding of the philosophical ideas that underlie the writing of the book. 4). Social Approach: This approach discusses the social impact of the book Fath Al Moein on Islamic society. Entries can discuss how this book influences the daily life practices of Muslims, the relationship between Muslims and Islamic law, and how society responds to this book. 5). Comparative Approach: This approach compares the Book of Fathul Muin with other fiqh books or with different fiqh approaches. These articles can identify the similarities and differences between this book and other books in terms of the method of writing, the legal sources used, and the uniqueness of the approach in the Book of Fathul Muin.

When conducting a theoretical study of the Book of Fathul Muin, it is important to choose a theoretical approach that fits the purpose of the article and can provide an in-depth understanding of the contents and context of the book.

METHODOLOGY

Researchers in this study decided to use research and development methods that fall into the category of combined research methods. There are several terms in the discussion of this developmental research. Ritchie and Kellen use the name R&D (research and design development). Thiagarajan uses a 4D model which stands for Define, Design, Develop and Publish. Has and promotes the use of the term ADDIE (Analysis, Design Development, Implementation Evaluation). Meanwhile, Borg and Gall are two figures who use the name R&D, which means Sugiono Development Research, (2015:28)

This understanding is different from the opinion of Nusa Putra (2011: 67) which says that research and development is defined as a method of deliberate and systematic research that aims to formulate, improve, develop, produce and test the effectiveness of certain superior, effective products. , efficient, productive and meaningful. The main studies in this study are observation (observation), interviews and documentation. Research and development (R&D) is a process or method used to validate and develop products. Hamzah, (2019: 45) R&D steps are potential problems, gathering product design information, design validation, design improvement, product trials, product

reviews, and trial use. While the development procedure is a preliminary study and typical development planning.

The research methodology or methodological approach that can be used in a certain book, Fath, is as follows: 1). Historical Approach: This method involves tracing and gathering information about the origins of a particular book of Fath, its author, and the historical context in which the book was written. For this reason, primary sources such as classic books and author biographies can be used as references. Secondary sources such as historical records, articles and previous research can also be used to gain a more complete understanding of the book. 2). Text Analysis Method: This method involves a detailed analysis of the contents of the Fathul Muin Book. Articles can investigate the legal arguments and concepts described in this book, and identify the opinions and arguments used by the author. This technique involves quoting and interpreting the text of the book accurately and critically. 3). Comparative approach: This method includes comparing the book of Fathul Muin with other fiqh books. Articles may compare the methods, legal opinions, or literary approaches used in this book with similar books. This technique makes it possible to assess the contribution and uniqueness of the Book of Fathul Muin in the context of Islamic fiqh literature. 4). Qualitative Approach: This method involves an in-depth investigation of the viewpoints, opinions and interpretations given in the Kitab Fathul Muin. Articles can interview fiqh experts or scholars who study this book or carry out qualitative data analysis such as the opinions of other scholars on this book. 5). Social Approach: This method involves researching the social impact of the book Fath Al-Maeen on the Islamic community. Articles may include interviews, notes or analysis of documents to understand how this book is used in the daily life of Muslims or legal decision-making.

The choice of research method depends on the purpose and focus of the article and the available sources. A combination of methods can also be used to gain a comprehensive understanding of a particular opening book.

RESULTS

Researchers in this study decided to use research and development methods that fall into the category of combined research methods. There are several terms in the discussion of this developmental research. Ritchie and Kellen use the name R&D (research and design development). Thiagarajan uses a 4D model which stands for Define, Design, Develop and Publish. Has and promotes the use of the term ADDIE (Analysis, Design Development,

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The choice of research method depends on the purpose and focus of the article and the available sources. A combination of methods can also be used to gain a comprehensive understanding of a particular opening book.

DISCUSSION

Research results in a particular book of Fath Search can cover the following aspects: 1. Analysis of the contents of the book: Search can include an in-depth analysis of the contents of a particular book of Fath, identification and explanation. It discusses topics and issues of legitimacy and various Islamic concepts. This can reveal the contribution of the Book of Fathul Muin in enriching the understanding of Islamic jurisprudence and law. 2. Evaluating the methodology and approach: This research was able to examine the approach and methodology used by the author of the Book of Fathul Muin in building propositions and compiling Islamic law. This can include assessing the correctness and accuracy of the approaches used, and their impact on the final output of the book. 3. Analysis of the arguments used: Articles can include an analysis of the arguments used in the Book of Fathul Muin. This can include exploring and discussing the arguments used by the author, as well as evaluating the strength and accuracy of the arguments cited. 4. Relevance of the Book of Fathul Muin to the social and time context: This research can analyze the significance of the Book of Fathul Muin in the current social context and time. This could include exploring whether the laws in the book are still relevant to the state and the development of modern society. 5. Scholars' and scholars' responses to books: Research can be in the form of tracing responses, criticisms, or recognition by scholars and scholars of certain conquered books. This can provide a further understanding of the acceptance and influence of the book among the clergy and the Muslim community. 6. Influence and Influence of the Book of Fathul Muin: This research can examine the impact and influence of the book of Fathul Muin on the understanding of Islamic law and the lives of Muslims. This could include exploring the use of books in making legal decisions, their application to religious practice, and their role in shaping Islamic thought and belief.

The results of research on the Book of Fathul Muin can provide insight into the content, methodology, relevance and influence of the book in scientific, social and religious contexts.

Research Findings Results

General Findings In this case, the researcher will present some general research results which will be used as a reference or initial study in the

development of Fath Al-Moeen teaching materials at the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School, Mungkid, Central Java, Manjkid, Central Java, as follows:

History of its Establishment

In this section, the researcher presents specific research findings regarding the application of special Fatah educational materials to increase the competence of students at the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School Mungkid, Central Java, Mungkid, Central Java and the supporting and inhibiting factors for the application of special Fatah. Teaching materials to improve the competence of Tanurunida Mungkid Islamic Boarding School students in Central Java according to the research focus.

Implementation of Fathul Muin's educational materials to improve the competence of students at the Tanwerunida Mungkid Islamic Boarding School, Central Java. During the research the researchers looked at the educational interactions that took place at the Tanwirunnida' Mungkid Islamic Boarding School, Central Java, there were educational materials used in educational books such as Fath Moin and other books in understanding and reading them.

Vision, Mission and Objectives of Pondok Pesantren Tanwirunnida' 1) Organizing Islamic boarding schools by upholding and developing Islamic values rohmatul lilalamin by upholding Pancasila values, the 1945 Constitution, the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, Unity in Diversity, justice, tolerance, humanity, sincerity, togetherness, and other noble values, to achieve the general goals of Islamic boarding schools that are in line with the vision, mission and goals of national development; and 2) Strive for and maintain the fulfillment of the elements of Islamic boarding schools (arkanul ma'had) and the soul or characteristics of Islamic boarding schools (rural ma'had) as applicable provisions.

The structure of the Ustadzsan of the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School
Secretariat: Rambeanak2 Hamlet, Rambeanak Village, Mungkid District,
Magelang Regency.

Gambar 1. Struktur Kepengurusan Pondok Pesantren Tanwirunnida'

Teaching materials in the designated opening

According to Ust. Moh. Zae Nurrofik Fathul Muin's educational materials explained In an interview on 22 July 2023, explained the following:

"The educational material in Fathul Muin is very difficult educational material both from the text editor and from the language used. Because it was written before the 20th century, at that time the pious scholar Zakariya al-Anshuri was famous for his language which was difficult and required deep reflection to understand. The educational material in Fathul Muin is of high quality and its implementation still requires a long and rigorous process. Apart from that, there must also be an Ustadz who always guides the students to understand it."

Based on the results of observations and interviews conducted by researchers, it can be concluded that the educational material in Fathul Muin is high-quality educational material and is included in the main subjects or is considered in class promotion and graduation in elementary schools. Tanwirunnida' Islamic Boarding School, in the learning process At Tanwirunnida' Mungkid Islamic Boarding School, Central Java has several classifications or levels of education including the curriculum is divided into three parts (components), first, the basic curriculum or (basic) is a curriculum

that includes the basics. subjects such as Mahou, horror and memorization. Second, the main curriculum (Ushuliyah) is a curriculum that includes basic subjects such as Usul al-Fiqh, Jurisprudence, Meditation, History, Tajweed, Sufism and Hadith. The third is a supportive or (integrative) curriculum, which includes supporting materials such as religious lectures, memorizing grammar and honors, practicing prayers, practicing meditation, praying, shrouds and burial of bodies, sports, arrow training, recitation of mourning and roti pul. read kanji.

Picture 2 : Source Fathul Muin, Kitab Fikih Populer Santri di Pesantren – LP
Maarif NU Jateng

Learning methods

The learning method that is often used is the lecture method. That is, this method is applied by lecturing or conveying information orally to students.

This method is the most practical and economical way and does not require a lot of tools.

“As stated by St. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. explain:

The teaching method with lectures aims to make teaching materials eye-opening not only to improve the quality of students and encourage an easy and fun learning process for both Ustadz and students. the ability of the students and the ability of the Ustadz Council to master subjects effectively. Because few students still don't understand the material you convey as highly as others. But his method is less effective”.

This is what Helmi also felt when he said:

“The learning method used in the application of Fath Al-Mu'min's educational materials is a lecture that focuses on only one direction, namely from Ustadz to students, causing a lack of understanding of the lesson and making you sleepy in class”.

Based on the results of the observations and interviews above, the researcher can conclude that the learning method applied by Pondok Pesantren Tanwirunnida uses the lecture method which focuses on only one Ustadz. However, in the process of implementing this method, it has many advantages, including Ustadz's can easily and freely monitor and control the situation or learning conditions of students in class. However, this method has weaknesses, namely, students get bored faster, are sleepy, and students do not understand.

Learning curriculum

When viewed from the time allocation and learning methods, the application of open-ended educational materials is something that is taken into account because it is related to the implementation of teaching and learning activities, Ust. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. explained: In an interview on 12 July 2023 that:

Starting from 2000, the study time for the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School was still integrated with public schools, namely from 07.30 to 13.30 WIB. The Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School began to have its class For public schools, for daiya activities in the morning from 7.30 to 0.11.00 WIB, but this has changed again in 2020, especially Islamic education in the afternoon from 12.30 to 0.16 00 WIB Because of its great influence regarding the application of Fathul Muin to teaching materials and learning methods that are still classic, namely the use of the lecture method has many weaknesses and not only that but also interpreted by students and read by their Ustadz against the yellow text of the book.

Based on the results of the observations and interviews above, the researcher can conclude that the curriculum implemented by Pondok Pesantren

Tanwirunnida' starting in 2000 is still below the ceiling of public schools, namely from 07.30 to 13.30 WIB. However, along with developments and changing times, study time at the Tannerunida Islamic Boarding School has begun to be separated from public schools, for one day's activities in the morning from 07.30 to 0.11.00 WIB. However, it has changed again in 2020 so far, namely Islamic religious education in the afternoon from 12.30 to 0.16 00 WIB. Because it is very influential on the application of educational material in Fath Al-Mu'in, as well as learning methods that are still traditional, namely the use of the lecture method which has many weaknesses and not only that but also students interpret it and their Ustadz read it against it. Yellow book text.

Learning assessment

In terms of assessing teaching materials for a 'certain conquest', the santri find it very difficult, as was experienced by Ust. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. explained: In an interview on 12 July 2023 that:

"The educational material in Fathul Muin is still far from the current curriculum because it is caused by several factors, namely delays in mastering Arabic grammar, students' interest in learning is very weak, the material provided is not interesting, and learning is just one way to cause boredom".

Meanwhile, according to Helmy, an evaluation of the application of Fatah's special education materials in an interview on 12 July 2023 explained as follows:

"The background to the application of Fathul Muin's educational materials at the Tanweerida Islamic Boarding School is that there are many students who only know the law without any argument. Many students complained that they did not understand the material presented by the Ustadzn. About this subject. The educational background of the santri in the past was that some graduated from elementary school, master and master. The Ustadz Council lacks mastery of the subject matter and devotes little time to it".

In line with that, the students also voiced Hilmi Fateh al-Maven's teaching material, as he conveyed in an interview on 12 July 2023, stating :

"Difficulties in understanding certain opening lessons are due to the inadequate mastery of grammar and adverbs, the language used by the Ustadz is not easy to understand, little study time especially during the day, many students are sleepy and the material is boring".

According to Helmy, the difficulties faced by the Book of Fathul Muin in educational materials are as follows:

“Difficulties in understanding the study of the Fathul Muin Book are due to inadequate mastery of grammar and adverbs, language that is difficult to digest and learning times that are not fun or boring”.

Based on the results of observations and interviews conducted by researchers regarding the evaluation of Fathul Muin's learning at the Tanurunida Islamic Boarding School, it consists of three components, namely first, the academic abilities of Ustadz or Ustadz. , because in the learning process, Ustadz has a very big role in implementing the learning process, apart from that Ustadz is also required to use various types of learning methods to provide understanding to students. Second, the data curriculum, curriculum has a very large influence, because it is a benchmark for the success of an educational institution starting from SK, KD, methods, time allocation and material taught and closing. Third, the background ability of the students, because the differences in the backgrounds of the students have an impact on the understanding of the material taught by the Ustadz, so the Ustadz must have various skills, both in how to deliver the material. or behavior towards students, and patience and persistence in guiding students.

This assessment connects three aspects, namely cognitive aspects, emotional aspects, and psychomotor aspects so that only one aspect is prioritized in the assessment of the three disciplines. Instead, attention should be paid to other aspects that must be considered when promoting and graduating from the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School.

Absorption capacity of students

Meanwhile, students' understanding of educational material in Fathul Muin is very important in the learning process of the material being taught. Because this is the benchmark for the company's success, as revealed by Ust. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. explained: In an interview on 12 July 2023 that: “The absorption capacity of Tannurunida Islamic Boarding School students for Fathul Muin's teaching materials is still lacking and can be said to be lower than the standard Islamic curriculum in general, both in terms of understanding and reading Arabic. According to my observations, this will be resolved if all the Ustadzs of the Tanwarunida Islamic Boarding School conduct a needs analysis and analyze the abilities of the students”.

This is in line with what was expressed by H. Daldiri as the Head of Men's Tanurunida Islamic Boarding School Development in an interview on 12 July 2023 explaining that:

“Absorption of educational material by students at the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School' Mungkid Central Java in Fathul Muin will be normal if school

education runs normally in terms of material absorption and management after operating between 4 to 10 years”.

As for the obstacles to implementing educational materials at Fath Al-Ma'in, the implementation process faces several obstacles, as revealed by the University of Applied Sciences. Ust. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. explained: In an interview on 12 July 2023 that:

“Obstacles in the process of applying Fateh Al-Maeen's teaching materials at the Tannerunida Islamic Boarding School include: the different backgrounds of the students and their special abilities, many students or students not knowing and understanding Arabic grammar and a large number of students or students prefer to play rather than study and managing the interior of the Undirected Tannerunida Islamic Boarding School”.

In another part, what makes it difficult for students to understand a topic is, as explained by Ust. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. said: In an interview on 12 July 2023, that:

“Some of the reasons students find it difficult to understand subjects, namely because their parents (mother and father) are so busy that the burden of family life cannot be carried properly are abandoned children, namely children who live 'wild' or are free in society because other people their parents are busy with farmland. Economically, they come from poor or orphaned families and have a strong desire from their parents to appear to be religiously intelligent and to be able to pray for them”.

While Helmy said among the students:

“The reason why students find it difficult to understand subjects, namely because they are busy with other activities or because there are so many activities that we don't focus on learning them and learning becomes boring”.

Based on the results of the observations and interviews above, students' understanding of fiqh and useful lessons is very low, as expressed by Sauma Rizqi and his friends, 'Fiqh and fiqh lessons are very difficult because they lack clarity. in the sense and the language used is not easy for us to understand, and we are also often sick and many are away.

DISCUSSION

When discussing articles in the book of Fathul Muin, several issues can be discussed as follows:

1. Contents of certain opening books: Articles can discuss in detail the contents of certain opening books. This includes the chapters or topics discussed in the book, the explanations of Islamic law contained therein, as well as the arguments and arguments used to support each discussion.
2. Legal approach

in the book: Articles can review the legal approach used in Fathul Muin's book. This includes the *ijtihad* methodology used by the author, the argumentative approach, as well as the methodology for compiling Islamic law. 3. Contribution of the book of Fathul Muin: The discussion may include the contribution of the book of Fathul Muin in the field of science or jurisprudence. This includes an explanation of how the book can provide an in-depth understanding of Islamic law, solve complex *fiqh* problems, or provide practical guidance in the daily lives of Muslims. 4. Comparison with other books: Articles can compare the Fathul Muin Book with other similar books or discuss similar topics. It can summarize the similarities and differences in approach, content or legal solution offered by a particular opening book. 5. Impact on society: The discussion may include the impact of Fathul Muin's book on society or the Muslim community. This could include how this book can be used by Islamic scholars or scholars in making legal decisions or providing religious advice to the public. 6. Relevance of the current book of Fatah: Articles can discuss the importance of the book Fathul Muin in the context of the life of Muslims today. Including the consideration of whether this book can still be used as a guide in dealing with new problems that arise in modern society. 7. Criticism and Evaluation: The discussion of the article may include a critical analysis of a particular book of Fath, from a scientific point of view and a social context. Including covering the advantages and disadvantages of this book and the response of scholars or scholars to it.

The discussion of the article on The Book of Fathul Muin should be carried out comprehensively providing accurate and in-depth information about the content, methodology and influence of this book on the lives of Muslims. In the tradition of Islamic boarding schools, especially Islamic boarding schools of the Salaf, there is a sequence of books that students need to study in various orders of Shari'a sciences. For example, in the science of *nahwu*, there are basic books, namely the book of *ijrumiyah*, then *smriti* to *aliyah*. In this article, we will discuss the book faithful main. Where this book usually becomes the number two order of books for students who want to study the classic book of the Shafi'i priest school. The order of the books is more or less like this: faithful main, faithful main and faithful Wahab. The three standard books just now are very popular in many Islamic boarding schools. Fathul Muin itself is a classic book of *fiqh* by Sheikh Zainuddin bin Abdul Aziz al-Malibari. Al-Malibari itself is the name of an area in India. This book is a Syrah book (commentary) from the book *Qurrotul 'ain*.

In terms of writing, the Book of faithful music has its own uniqueness compared to other *fiqh* books. From the initial discussion alone, Sheikh

Zainuddin wrote the prayer chapter first. This is very different from fiqh books in general, which usually discuss the rules of purification (taharah) in the first chapters. Besides that, the Book of Faithful Main is also known as a book that is quite difficult in placing the reference of a homer (pronoun). In discussing the conditions of prayer for example. If we examine the fiqh books in general, the conditions for prayer have certain chapters or fasl and the discussion doesn't go anywhere.

But this is very different in the book faithful main. On page four of the book Fathul Mu'in, we are presented with a discussion of the meaning of the first terms and conditions that must be met before praying. What makes this book different is that the final discussion of the conditions for prayer ends on page 15. Even though at first glance there are only five conditions for prayer, namely facing the Qibla; cleaning the body, clothing and unclean places, cleaning from small and large hats, centering prayer times and covering the genitals. But when explaining one by one, still drop by for other discussions. For example, the condition for prayer must be holy from small habits, of course, this discussion is still related to the chapter on ablution', so in that chapter the discussion also describes ablution and its details. Such as procedures, traditions, and things that cancel to cases that are interesting and important topics from the ablution chapter itself.

No wonder, if this book is not systematic. For scholars and connoisseurs of fiqh, there are challenges in studying line by line from the book of faithful main. We are invited to think and reflect on the treasures of Islamic scholarship, the legacy of the Salafunas Sholihin scholars, which are different from most books. In addition, there are several "signs", a kind of discussion terminal in the book faithful main. The terminal for this discussion will usually be bolded in the writing in the book. This discussion terminal is like a bus/public transportation terminal in cities, a place to stop, start and stop (sign, red) that needs to be underlined.

There is a discussion terminal called Var'un. Far'un's simple language is a branch problem. So when we discuss unclean chapters, for example, Sheikh Zainuddin will discuss certain cases that are common in society in general. He explained it in detail. In addition, there are also those named tasbih (warning) and faith (benefits). So, in this terminal tannin, the author of the book seems to warn that the discussion under discussion contains a very important note. For example, the discussion about the permissibility of not praying in congregation. Now, when there is tasbih, mushonnif then explains the importance of explaining the legal statement of excuses for not carrying out congregational prayers because there are scholars who punish congregational prayers as

fardhu ain, so it is necessary to explain excuses for the permissibility of not praying in congregation and he is not guilty if there is an excuse that has been explained.

In addition, there is also the term Noida. Syekh Zainuddin in his work inserts the application of fiqh rules so that it makes it easier for us to learn fiqh. As the rule on page 13 reads:

أَنَّ مَا أَصْلُهُ الطَّهَارَةُ وَغَلَبَ الظَّنُّ تَنَجُّسُهُ لِعَلِيَّةِ النَّجَاسَةِ فِي مِثْلِهِ قَوْلَانِ مَعْرُوفَانِ يَقُولِي الْأَصْلُ وَالطَّاهِرُ أَوْ الْغَالِبُ أَرْجَحُهُمَا أَنَّهُ طَاهِرٌ

Meaning: the origin of something is if it is holy and most likely then there is something that pollutes it, then there are two famous quotes: following the original law (sacred) and its evil law (unclean). The most superior of the two opinions is sacred.

The text of the book above is an implementation of the fiqh rules:

الأصل بقاء ما كان على ما كان

Meaning: the law of origin is the persistence of something over the previous state.

So, when we find cases of doubt like the case in the Fathul Muin book earlier, we can simply argue with these fiqh rules. Lastly, is Fatimah or Muhammad (perfect/important)? So one of the habits of Sheikh Zainuddin before ending the discussion is that there is a Fatimah or Muhammad terminal as the completion of the fall. If the students want to easily learn the book of Fathul Muin, the students usually use the book Ianah Ath-Tholibin as hasyiyah or marginal notes from the book Fathul Muin. As the name means helper for students, this book of Isaiah ath-thali bin is very helpful for students to study the book fathul muin which is quite complicated and different from most other fiqh books. There is even an anecdote or advice from the ustadz that I remember regarding the book of faithful main. It reads like this, "whoever reads faithful main fluently, God willing, will easily understand fiqh from other books. Because the language of fish books is not much different. Because the language of faithful main is difficult, while other books are not as difficult as faithful main."

In addition, "whoever studies the book of Fathul Muin but does not hold or refer to the book of Syrah, namely the book of Isaiah ath-thali bin, then he is arrogant. Understanding the Book of faithful main is difficult if it is not accompanied by the Book of Isaiah. Thus, it still doesn't feel right if there are figures of Santri, researchers to fiqh experts who claim to start to feel deep in

their religious knowledge if they don't also have a deep understanding of their fiqh in the book Faithful main

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusion of the article about the Book of Fathul Muin at the Tanurunida Islamic Boarding School can vary depending on the argumentation and purpose of the writing. However, several possible conclusions can be drawn from the article: 1. The Book of Fathul Muin is one of the important fiqh books in Islamic heritage. This book discusses various aspects of Islamic law, such as worship, affairs, and family matters. 2. The authors of the book, such as Sheikh Zakaria Al-Ansari, used a directed approach and structured method, and referred to well-known and widely recognized sources of Islamic law. 3. The Book of Fathul Muin has a great influence on Islamic society. This book can be used as a reference by scholars and practitioners of Islamic law in understanding Islamic law and deciding legal issues. 4. Even though the Book of Fathul Muin has great influence, there are criticisms and questions about the opinions and interpretations described in this book. This criticism can be attributed to the suitability of opinions within the social and cultural context, as well as the expansion of the broader scope of Islamic law. In conclusion, the essay can provide an in-depth understanding of the contents of the Fathul Muin Book, the method of writing, and explanations of legal analysis, as well as the influences and criticisms of this book. Conclusions can also provide the author's response to the problem, and raise questions or directives for further research regarding a particular opening book.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so that research still needs to be done on the following titles "Implementation of Fathul Muin's Teaching Material Books to Improve Santri Competence at Tanwirunnida' Mungkid Islamic Boarding School, Central Java".

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